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“Philosophical Foundations of Bioethics”

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- Evaluation of Bioethical Principles and Values -

Abstract: Here, in these essays, I make a critique of wanting to transvalue and to also consider bioethical values, considering Humean metaphysics, the arguments of “Arthur Schopenhauer” that I see pertinent to it (with a brief consideration of I. Kant) and the article by “Tom L. Beauchamp” “THE FOUR PRINCIPLES APPROACH TO HEALTH CARE ETHICS” of his book “Standing on principles”; which enunciates, reviews and comments on the four current principles of bioethics. I do also bring Nietzsche’s work into the discussion. It is a translation, editing and rewriting of an old work of Graduation of 2013.

Keywords: Ethics, Bioethics, Hume, Schopenhauer, Beauchamp, Nietzsche, Principles, Maleficence, Autonomy.

- About “David Hume”, his Ethics and Metaphysics -

Some could say, erroneously, that Humean ethics is an untouched sphere for all the author's metaphysical discussion subjects, but this is nothing more than a big mistake that leads to more and more errors and misinterpretations of the Humean corpus and of his ethical thinking. It can be seen in the following essay that Humean metaphysics is a *conditio sine qua non* to its ethics. I will discuss the relationship between the actions of a moral agent and the relevance to which his free will, if possible, entails his responsibility for his actions and judgments.

- “David Hume” on ‘Free Will’ -¹

The core of “Hume's” compatibilist theory of ‘free will’ and ‘determinism’ is apparently based on the following conclusions:

- Actions that may be under the scrutiny of moral judgment are not distinguishable from others by an absence of cause, but rather by a different *type* of cause. Free or responsible moral actions are caused by our own wills, while

¹ The following section is based mostly on this reference: Cohon, Rachel, “Hume's Moral Philosophy”, *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Fall 2010 Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall_2010/entries/hume-moral/>.

unfree actions are performed by causes external to the agent. I will call this argument that seeks to conclude this the “argument from spontaneity”.

- A ‘freedom’ which means a ‘denial of necessities and causes’ (*A Treatise of Human Nature*, 2.3.2.1/407) does not exist and would make morality impossible. I will call this argument that seeks to conclude this “anti-libertarian”.
- Necessity, properly understood, is the constant conjunction of objects, and the inference of the mind from one object to another. (*A Treatise of Human Nature*, 2.3.1.4/400; *Enquiry Concerning Human Understanding*, 8.5/82). I will call this argument which attempts to conclude this the “argument from necessity”.

These seem to be the arguments that define the basis of “Hume’s” compatibilist strategy. Let us see, then, how he positions himself in relation to “freedom”, from which he distinguishes two possible freedoms:

“Few are capable of distinguishing betwixt the liberty of spontaneity, as it is call’d in the schools, and the liberty of indifference; betwixt that which is oppos’d to violence, and that which means a negation of necessity and causes. The first is even the most common sense of the word; and as ‘tis only that species of liberty, which it concerns us to preserve, our thoughts have been principally turn’d towards it, and have almost universally confounded it with the other.” (*The Treatise of Human Nature*, 2.3.2.1/407-408).

“Hume’s” point here is that free actions are those “caused by the wills and desires of the agent”. We determine, in this view, that an agent is responsible for his actions when they are determined by his wishes and wants in question. Therefore, an action is voluntary or involuntary in the same sense, therefore, there is no incompatibility between an action that is determined by a causal network and the free

action of an agent that is responsible for it. On the contrary, free and responsible moral actions *require* that an agent has caused them through his will and volition. A coerced agent, although he is in the necessary causal network, therefore, cannot be accused of the action he performed because he did not want to perform such and such action (*A Treatise of Human Nature*, 2.3.2.6/411), therefore, this agent is not responsible for such actions. This is the so-called ‘argument from spontaneity’ that I name it here. Therefore, the ‘argument from spontaneity’ aims to distinguish ‘free action’ from ‘unfree’ not on the grounds that the former has no cause (as suggested in the conception of ‘freedom through indifference’), or is uncaused, but that would have a cause of a different *type* than the second.

But in *Enquiry concerning Human Understanding* (8.23/95) the definition of freedom becomes more problematic when he makes it distinct from those in the *Treatise*, for example, the distinction here between ‘spontaneous freedom’ and ‘indifferent freedom’ is replaced as follows:

“By liberty, then we can only mean a power of acting or not acting, according to the determinations of the will; that is, if we choose to remain at rest, we may; if we choose to move, we also may. Now this hypothetical liberty is universally allowed to belong to everyone who is not a prisoner and in chains .”

Therefore, ‘freedom of spontaneity’ does not guarantee ‘hypothetical freedom’, because, one would say that ‘although I want to leave or stay in this room, it could still be the case that if I wanted to leave I might not, because the door could be locked’. In “Hume’s” view ‘hypothetical freedom’ thus provides a compatibilism of free will with plausible situations in which ‘spontaneous freedom’ would be nullified by external factors.

The 'anti-libertarian' argument continues from several of the considerations of the 'spontaneous freedom' argument. The 'anti-libertarian argument' defends the thesis that the libertarian position presents a fatal error. 'Freedom of indifference', as I defined it and, according to "Hume", is "that which means a denial of necessity and causes". This position advocates that a moral action cannot be caused or necessitated. However, this position cannot be based on moral responsibility, as understood by "Hume". If one removes the necessity of actions, therefore, he will also cut off the causes of them. It seems clear to him that no one can be held responsible for actions to which he contributed nothing, so the libertarian must answer what is the mechanism or source of responsibility for an action; this is a difficulty he must overcome. In these arguments presented, which are traditionally called 'arguments of freedom', the position will be defended that it is unreasonable or irrational to accuse an agent of an action which he had no desire to carry out; precisely what one would say when performed because of external violence or indifference. This account of the 'arguments of liberty' serves as the foundation of the classical interpretations of the compatibilist strategy of "Hume".

Incompatibilists have described Hume's "freedom-will" position as "I. Kant" famously declared, that this "freedom" would be no different from the freedom which a clock has to move its arrows according to the internal causes of its mechanisms, this position, therefore, would be no more than a subterfuge... These incompatibilists, then, would argue that if our wills and choices are determined by antecedent causes, therefore, we could never choose otherwise as we choose. Given prior causes or causal conditions, therefore, we would have to act exactly as we did. Therefore, we cannot be held responsible for our actions, as we had no 'genuine alternatives' or other possibilities available to us so that we could act differently.

The "argument of necessity" argues that there would appear to be a:

“...conjunction between ‘motives’ and ‘voluntary actions’ is as regular and uniform as that between the cause and effect in any part of nature; but also that this ‘regular conjunction’ has been universally acknowledged among mankind, and has never been the subject of dispute, either in philosophy or common life.” (Enquiry concerning Human Understanding, 8.16/88) - I have highlighted here some words and expressions for my purposes.

Therefore, “Hume” tries to demonstrate that this “regular conjunction” between ‘motive’ and ‘action’ allows inference in the moral sphere by determining one and from this, therefore, the other; as in this passage: *“determining us to infer the existence of one from that of another” (A Treatise of Human Nature, 2.3.1.14/404)*. The arguments that “Hume” uses here are based by him on two “incontestable” facts, that *“men always seek society” (A Treatise of Human Nature, 2.3.1.8/402)*, and men regard other people as objects of ‘praise’ or ‘blame’ - that is, hold them accountable. In order for people to live in society, he argues, they must make moral inferences about the character of others and - in opposition to this, but parallel to - for people to hold others responsible they must infer character from actions. Hume argues that men are mutually dependent on each other so that almost none of their actions is complete in itself, or without the reflection of the actions of others, and this would be a requirement for the intention of the actions of another person or agent. He proceeds, then, to want to demonstrate that we make these kinds of inferences:

“In all those conclusions [expectations concerning the actions of others] they take their measures from past experience, in the same manner as in their reasonings concerning external objects; and firmly believe that men, as well as all the elements, are to continue, in their operations, the same that they have ever found them.” (Enquiry concerning Human Understanding, 8.17/89).

Thus he goes on to argue that inferences in the moral sphere are no less certain than those in the natural sphere. He then states: *"nothing but a conclusion concerning the actions of men, deriv'd from the consideration of their motives, temper and situation"* (*A Treatise of Human Nature*, 2.3.1.15/404). Therefore, this kind of "reason" would be pertinent to politics, war, commerce, economy and so on, in such a way that they would be so connected to human activities that it would be impossible to act or subsist at any moment without considering it.

Consequently, Hume again argues against libertarians, saying that if we advocated 'freedom of indifference', society would not be possible. He will try to argue against the incompatibilists, that their mistake in their charge is to confuse necessity as it is found in or 'exists in matter', or in phaenomena. He infers that this type of necessity is unique to 'insensible matter', which would be tied to the supposed 'unintelligible necessity'. The 'necessity' of the will for him, therefore, would be proper to the mind alone, he imputes this 'necessity' to it alone and not to matter, or material objects.

The sense then defended by him is that traditional metaphysics has confused this 'cause' with someone who is 'compelled to' such an action. Therefore, he reiterates that a free and responsible action must be caused by the agent's will and not obligated.

As can be seen above, “Hume” categorically reiterates that morality would be impossible, or rather, not merely it, but its ethics would be impossible without the considerations of the above analysing essay on ‘free will’.

Below it is possible to contemplate the arguments of “Schopenhauer” against ‘free will’, which start from the consideration of the ‘empiricist tradition’ and collapse in his idealism which is strongly influenced by the latter. I will make considerations and connections between “Hume” and “Schopenhauer” just below before presenting the arguments, thinking about them both and then presenting them and reaching the conclusion with which I agree.

- *On Passions and Will* -

Hume tries to reconcile that human actions are determined by causal networks of necessary connections between causes, or objects, and their effects - on other affected objects. The arguments presented and translated (on the original article in Portuguese) are from the works “*A Treatise of Human Nature*” and “*Enquiry concerning Human Understanding*”. The development of the argument is coherent in both works, although the “doctrine of liberty” as it is formulated in “*A Treatise of Human Nature*” is appraised by the author as absurd and unintelligible... In both works, he argues that just as we discover the necessity (in this sense) to maintain motion between material bodies, we discover so much necessity to perform among human motives, character traits, and the circumstances of action on the one hand, and human behaviour on the other.

He says in the “*Treatise*” that ‘freedom of indifference’ is the negation of ‘necessity’, in this sense, that this is the notion of freedom which he labels absurd, and

identifies with luck or randomness (which cannot be a real power in nature, supposedly), both in the *“Treatise”* and the first *“Enquiry”* (epistemological). Human actions are not free in this sense. However, “Hume” in the *“Treatise”* will allow men to be free at times in the sense of freedom that is opposed to violence or constraint. This is the sense in which “Hume” focuses on *“EcHU”*: *“a power to act or not to act, according to the determinations of the will;”* that everyone has *“who is not a prisoner and is in chains”* (*“EcHU”* 8.1.23, the emphasis of “Hume”).

According to the classic account, “Hume’s” effort to articulate the conditions of moral responsibility, and the way they relate to the problem of free will, is to be understood primarily in terms of his views on the logic of our concepts of “freedom” and “necessity”. Free and responsible action, it is said, must be caused by the agent. There is therefore no incompatibility between free will and determinism. “Hume” believed that in these arguments causal necessity and freedom were compatible, however, as we will see later, I take that this position is nothing more than wishful thinking.

- “Schopenhauer” on Free Will –²

I will present here in a superficial way some arguments from the work “On Freedom of the Will” (in German: *Über die Freiheit des Willens menschlichen*) which is an essay presented to the “Royal Norwegian Society of Science” in 1839 by “Arthur Schopenhauer” as an answer to the academic question they had posed: “Is it possible to demonstrate human free will through self-consciousness?” It is a component of rehearsals in his work “*Die beiden Grundproblem der Ethik*”. The Schopenhauerian position is clear when it comes to free will in relation to what is phenomenal or to the will and motives, its answer is negative in the entirety of the possibility of free will in men. In relation to conscience and abstract thought, there is relative free will «for they are not appearances».

“Schopenhauer” begins his strategy of analysis of the basic concepts of “freedom” and “self-consciousness”. He stated that there are three types of freedom, that are, physical, intellectual, and moral:

- ‘Physical freedom’ is the absence of material obstacles or bodies to action. This is generally thought to constitute freedom of the will (and this would be what “Hume” understands as “free will” in a certain sense of his).

² This section will be based on the following references: Schopenhauer, Arthur, *On the Freedom of the Will*, Oxford: Basil Blackwell ISBN 0-631-14552-4.

- ‘Intellectual freedom’ is possible when the mind has clear knowledge or can think of abstract or concrete motives for action. This occurs or is possible when the mind is unaffected, for example, by extreme passion (*exempli gratia*, profound rage over an injustice) or mind-altering substances (such as alcohol, cocaine or prescription drugs).
- ‘Moral freedom’ is when there are no influences of motives on a person’s actions, *id est*, this would suppose that the person is free to choose a course of action without no cause whatsoever! In other words, as if one could choose his own will.
- ‘Self-consciousness’ is his or her awareness of one’s own will and that which one desires, including one’s emotions and passions. That is the subject has clear knowledge of what is his intentions, and desires (be it a concrete object, being, imagination, the emotion of approval or acceptance, the will to reflect on the Nature of anything whatsoever, &c.).

According to “Schopenhauer”, when a person inspects his or her self-awareness «or self-conscience», he or she encounters the feeling of “I can do whatever I want as long as I am not hindered”. But “Schopenhauer” stated that this is merely physical freedom. He said: “You can do what you want, but at a given moment in your life, you can want only one definite thing and absolutely nothing else.” So the answer to the Norwegian academy was a “no”, certainly a “no” also for the Humean tradition.

On the other hand, when a person observes the outside World «in the sense that he is experiencing different events, happenings, and deeds of or onto himself, and onto others», he or she finds that every change has been preceded by a change in another. This sequence or chain of events is perceived as the necessary effect that follows and its

antecedent respective cause. According to Schopenhauer, men are affected by three types of causes:

- ‘Cause’ in the strictest sense of the word relates to mechanical, physical and chemical changes in an inorganic or non-living biological object. According to the scientific understanding of the time of “Schopenhauer”, he believed that the “Laws of Motion” of “I. Newton” described the respective phenomena.
- ‘Stimulus’ is an alteration that produces a reaction in an organism that is devoid of knowledge, such as in plants (although this is an example, any organism, or most organisms at the very least are able to react to a stimulus). It requires physical contact; in other words, the movement of the cause which is the stimulus, such as a wave of light or a wave of heat, touches the organelles or organs of that being. The effect is related to or is proportional to the duration and intensity of the stimulus. - This position can be questioned in the sense that plants communicate even with animals, but for practical purposes, a plant does not have a neural ganglion and therefore, arguably, does not have language or audible and perhaps corporeal intelligence. Therefore, this position, considering the scientific epoch of “Schopenhauer”, is not problematic.
- ‘Motivation’ is the causality that passes through or happens to a sentient spirit (or ‘mind’ as some wanted to define it). The motive just needs to be realized, no matter how long, how close, or how different it presents itself or shows itself. For animals, the reason must be immediately present. Human beings (the other animals), however, can also respond to motives that are abstract concepts, or abstract ideas, imagination, and mere thoughts. Therefore, human beings are capable of deliberation in which a strong abstract motive or idea trumps other motives and necessarily determines the will to act; in a sense that this

compelling idea is so much stronger than any other motive. This is relative freedom in which human beings are not determined by objects that are immediately presented to them or present, if and only if considering those ideas and thoughts are stronger motives and the presence or absence of external objects or other beings present do not compel the human being into acting in relation or onto that which is external to him.

Here is a passage from chapter III of the essay:

“I can do what I will: I can, if I will, give everything I have to the poor and thus become poor myself—if I will! But I cannot will this, because the opposing motives have much too much power over me for me to be able to. On the other hand, if I had a different character, even to the extent that I were a saint, then I would be able to will it. But then I could not keep from willing it, and hence I would have to do so.”

As well as this other passage from the same chapter:

“[A]s little as a ball on a billiard table can move before receiving an impact, so little can a man get up from his chair before being drawn or driven by a motive. But then his getting up is as necessary and inevitable as the rolling of a ball after the impact. And to expect that anyone will do something to which absolutely no interest impels them is the same as to expect that a piece of wood shall move toward me without being pulled by a string.”

Every man has a unique way of reacting to every motive - he argues. This is called or named by the word ‘character’ (the word character, from Ancient Greek, meant as well ‘spirit’ or ‘tone’ of a person). It is the nature, or essence, the very truth of an individual’s will. The human character, as “Schopenhauer” defines it, has four attributes:

- ‘Individual’ - as an intellectual capacity, each person’s character is unique, therefore they are different characters. Acts cannot be predicted just by knowing the motives. Individual character knowledge is also necessary in order to predict what will be the deeds of a person or how a person will act.
- ‘Empirical’ - The character of other people or oneself must be experienced so that one can know their nature, they can only be known through experience. Only by seeing an actual deed, or action of someone or oneself (or perceiving others or oneself) actual behaviour in a given situation can the character be known or determined. This is analogous to an analysis of a cause through its effects.
- ‘Constant’ - The character is immutable, or unalterable, it does not change. It remains the same and will continue to be constant in nature, despite any event that may happen, throughout life. This is assumed whenever a person is evaluated, or is analysed in a critical way, or logical way, through the result of his previous actions, *id est*, his deeds are analysed or evaluated as the effects of a possible cause, which would be his character. Given the same situations, events, or circumstances, what was done once will be repeated again and again; if an assassin has killed before, this can be done again and it will, given a similar scenario. Behaviour, however, can change or will be altered when a character learns to achieve his goal through a different way of acting, in other words, if there are other ways possible to reach a destiny, it’s a possible path. The means, or the ways, or strategy change, but not the ends. This is the result of learning by the teachings or instruction by others, or improved cognition, or education.
- ‘Innate’ - Characters are like essences of a will, they are like a granite stone determined by nature, not the environment nor can they be learned. Two people

who were raised in the exact same environment, were taught the same things, and experienced the same things, will expose different characters (this is even true for monozygotic or so-called identical twins).

Therefore, virtue or the values of Good and Evil cannot be taught to anyone. The tendency to “good” and “evil”, or in other words, malevolent or benevolent will and their consequent deeds is an innate result of character. Are two deeds possible for a given person under the same given situation or circumstances? Definitely not. A person can only make or do or choose to realise one deed according to a will she or he has not chosen. Since a person's character cannot be altered and remains unchanged, if the circumstances of his life were not altered or remained unchanged (his life continues on its course as if it were the same as before), could his life change, be another or have been any different? No. Everything that happens, happens necessarily and could not be otherwise; for if it could be otherwise it wouldn't have been effected in such a way as it is exactly now. That would presuppose that a fact could be otherwise than it is, and this would constitute a contradiction, since every fact has a cause or sufficient reason as to why it is as it is. Through what men do and what we do, we find out and discover what we are. To wish that some event had not occurred is ridiculous and foolish self-torture, for it is the desire for an absolutely impossible thing. Finally, there is another big mistake we make: It is a mistake to think that abstract motives, that is, abstract volitions have no necessary effects, because they are just thoughts. This error results in the illusion that we can be conscious of having free will, when in fact we have a relative freedom, but we ourselves do not choose these rational volitions and ideas, they flow through our spirits out of our control. In fact, the most powerful abstract volition or idea (or motive or cause) necessarily determines concrete action; as in this passage from Chapter III:

“Let's imagine a man who, while on the street, said to himself: “It's six o'clock at night, the workday is over. Now I can go for a walk, or I can go to the club; I can also go up the tower to see the sunset, I can go to the theatre, I can visit this friend or that friend; indeed, I too may run out the door, into the wide world, and never come back. All this is strict and it is up to me, in this I have complete freedom. But still, I won't do any of these things now, but of my own free will I will return home to my wife.””

From then on, “Schopenhauer” will try to defend the responsibility of our actions before the beings in the World, appealing to “Kant”. Everybody feels intimately in themselves that they are responsible for their deeds, otherwise, they could have done something completely different than what they had chosen to affirm and do. In this sense, we feel responsible for anything we make or do, and, in fact, we should feel this way. Schopenhauer then argues that this feeling of moral responsibility and freedom can coexist with the necessity of our deeds. In his “Critique of Pure Reason” (A533-558) and “Critique of Practical Reason” (Chap. III), “Kant” will defend: When a person has a mental image of himself as a phaenomenon existing in the lived and experienced world, his deeds appear to be rigorously determined or be the result, or consequences of causes, reasons or motives that affect his character. This is an empirical necessity, and it follows that for them to be responsible for their deeds, their will, their choices and actions must be attributable to them. But when that person feels within himself as a ‘thing-in-itself’, not as a phaenomenon, he thus feels free. According to “Schopenhauer”, it is because the ‘inner being’ or ‘thing-in-itself’ is called the will. This word “will” designates the closest analogy with what is felt to be the interior and essence of a person. When we feel in ourselves our will, we are transcendently free; and in this sense, not just as appearances. So, according to “Schopenhauer”, we have the responsibility for our deeds, because we are the result of our inner essence and being (we are the result of our

will), which is a transcendental free will. We were made, in other words, by our transcendental will. As he says - which leads us to the criticism of "Schopenhauer" himself -:

"Man does at all times only what he wills, and yet he does so necessarily. But this is because he *is already* this will."

However, we could raise the objection that "Nietzsche" makes to the Kantian and Schopenhauerian metaphysical goal about the total indeterminacy of the "thing-in-itself", or raise it to "Schopenhauer" for having denied it precisely for having determined it. For "Kant" the "thing-in-itself" are not phaenomenic objects, they are not objects by representation, they are not the principles of the intellect, nor essences or ideas, leading "Nietzsche" to the sharp decision of saying that speaking of something absolutely indeterminate is the same as speaking about nothing; that, therefore, the "thing-in-itself" is a non-existent fantasy.

After this indispensable discussion, I see the matter that falls on bioethical principles as pertinent; I will talk about the "Respect for Autonomy" and "Non-Maleficence" Principles.

- The Principle of Respect for Autonomy -

"Tom L. Beauchamp" seems to define "autonomy" as follows: "Autonomy means freedom from external constraint and the presence of critical mental capacities such as

understanding, intending, and voluntary decision making. The autonomous individual acts freely in accordance with a self-chosen plan, analogous to the way an independent government manages its territories and sets its policies. A person of diminished autonomy, by contrast, is in some respect controlled by others or incapable of deliberating or acting on the basis of his or her desires and plans.”³ Beauchamp says this principle is rooted in the liberal tradition that gives individual freedom and personal choice great importance. Here, as already explained and considering the influence of “Schopenhauer”, this definition of the “autonomous” individual as acting “freely” is nothing more than a more obvious wishful thinking in a similar manner how it is presented in the Humean discourse. If you look at the person with limited or null “autonomy”, whether due to psychophysiological incapacity, or due to coercion, in my opinion, it would be more apt to speak of ‘consent’ in favour or not of, for example, therapy or surgical intervention and not speak in terms of ‘autonomy’... Even if the person undergoes medical treatment and obtains or has a technical understanding of the procedures, still, he will not be free to make the best decision (the best consent), as he cannot choose to want what would be the best decision for him; or rather, the decision which, according to his experiences, led him to act according to sensations. In his view, by induction, it will be the most likely to succeed with minimal risks, or even, perhaps, the riskiest, but with the greatest chance of success (sometimes [this does not entail rareness] it is even the riskiest with a considerable low chance of success). As the refutation of “autonomy” also falls to all other non-patient humans, that is, to doctors alike and their teams (and animals) - in the specific case not of research, but of care for patients who want to be attended -, if they have the genuine feeling and delight in

³ Pg 37. Beauchamp, T., 2010. *Standing on principles*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

making their patients' bodies-and-psyches healthy, then they will do absolutely everything in their power to achieve their goals. If they fail, they will have no reason to blame themselves, for they will have done everything in their power, and would only be worthy of punishment if they failed through negligence. At random the moralist might ask: 'What about the 'patients' perspective and belief positions?' Would he say, 'Aren't they violating my will?' We could answer it with two more pertinent questions: 'Is it intuitive that the patient came to give his trust in the medical authority because he did not want to perish, but to become healthy?' And more: 'Wouldn't doctors be hypocrites for denying the best possible treatment to those other hypocrites who wanted and didn't want to be treated?' In the heart of a medical research, I only see as relevant the research of a technique, treatment, new procedure, among others, that appear as absolutely new in their endeavour. If research uses men as guinea pigs to know the multiple varying effects between those who receive a drug, for example, and this chemical compound is absolutely new, then, in a Humean empiricist sense, we could not know *à priori* the effects of that cause. In fact, we would not know, except by mere induction, the chances of effects of various causes, even because the relations of causes and effects occur in bodies with similar characteristics, and, even if it were possible for them to be identical to each other, we could still *à priori* expect any effects whatsoever, including no apparent effects.

Therefore, informing patients of possible effects would only be speculation, even if they were knowledgeable about medicine. Research that seeks to clarify new effects on old drugs violates every record of previous medical studies, and bets on something that no scientist bets, even more so in the pharmaceutical field, the non-contiguity between past and future, in which the future (and there is no contradiction in

this) the effects of the drugs observed before would be endowed with absolutely different effects than predicted.

It is precisely in this light of the impossibility of being sure about a patient's autonomy but, rather, taking into account what really matters is the person's consent; if she is a person who has been offered treatment, or if her family, society or the State thinks that she 'should' be treated, *exempli gratia*, 'as in a psychiatric case', or in another example, a medical experiment, let her consent first (otherwise other solution should be found and sought). For if this would not be I would classify and understand this as a violence of a level as serious as rape. And in real cases, in the crudest instance of life, most doctors would commit many errors and many acts of violence, as is ubiquitously known to be the case today.

Here I make an intersection about the "Genealogy of Morals" by "Nietzsche" and then talk about the "Principle of Non-Maleficence", as it is pertinent to this criticism to speak of this work when I refer to transvaluing the values presented here.

- The Genealogy of Morals -⁴

I would like to speak briefly about this Nietzschean work, as I see it as pertinent to other principles as well as the previous one. It is composed of three essays on morality: the genesis of morality, its development and crystallization, and its perishing.

I

In the first essay, a type of Hobbesian “state of nature” is presented in which morality is reduced to a power struggle... The ‘nobles’, unlike the ‘slaves’, would be those endowed with power over other people and things in the World, and therefore would despise those who did not possess similar characteristics; the latter would be the weak and the plebeians. Therefore, values originated in power, the nobles, for being able to conquer, named people, things and actions ‘bad’ or ‘good’ - these were acts of power and conquest. What or who was conquered was by definition ‘bad’ and the respective conquerors ‘good’... Images of Hómeros’ Iliad come to mind as he presents these arguments.

On the other hand, the antinomies ‘good’ and ‘evil’ would have been created by the slaves themselves to take revenge on the nobles - and for envying them -, because

⁴ This section will be based on the following reference: *On The Genealogy of Morals and Ecce Homo*, translated and edited by [Walter Kaufmann](#) (translation of *On the Genealogy* in collaboration with [R. J. Hollingdale](#)), New York: Vintage, 1967; this version also included in *Basic Writings of Nietzsche*, New York: Modern Library, 2000, [ISBN 0-679-72462-1](#).

the former lacked, precisely, the power of the nobles. Through envy and a sense of their own powerlessness, resentment grew in the slaves' hearts for hating their misery of powerlessness. It should be noted that slaves hated their own impotence. And then they discovered that they had power over the psychological realm; therefore, the slaves could overthrow the nobles through their skills and intelligence about the psychological realm of men...

II

Values were once amoral *in stricto-sensu*, and were derived through the legal sphere; here "Nietzsche" defines 'guilt' as "a bad conscience". The World of moral concepts of 'guilt', 'conscience', 'duty' and 'the sanctity of duty' thus had the same legal origin; by the "sphere of legal obligations", or as he defines it, the socio-political realm. It was in this kingdom that promises were made and in which memory was *made* for those who promised. Humanity had then created the need to hold people accountable for their actions. Buyers and sellers and all members of society required means that their debts would not be paid, that they would not be burdened, that they would not be betrayed, and that they would not fall into danger into the hands of others. Through a contract, the debtor gave confidence to the creditor that his debt would be paid, and that the promise would be fulfilled, "ensuring the sanctity and seriousness of the promise" (Genealogy of Morals, First Essay, 17-18), making the impression of payment as 'duty', a supposed obligation upon his 'conscience'. 'Guilt', 'conscience' and 'duty' were - as already stated - amoral and legal terms: 'Guilt' was the debt to be paid, 'duty' was the

necessity to submit to the prevailing legal system, and 'conscience' was the mechanism for preventing infringements of the legal system.

'Guilt' and 'conscience' only became moral concepts in the hands of the 'weak', whereas the 'strong' would be those 'masters of themselves', which 'Nietzsche', by definition, declares to be those who are endowed with a powerful "freedom instinct", or "will to power". The strong, therefore, would be those in agreement with themselves, establishing, preserving, and making known their independence in the world and who, for that, would have to overcome obstacles in their paths; they would be frank with themselves in asserting their wishes, *id est*, reciprocal with their psychological materials. The strong, by overcoming obstacles and affirming their will, affirm themselves as they exist, or as they came to exist, and do not remake themselves as they are not. They adapt the World to themselves and do not submit to merely having to adapt to it. The weak lack what the 'master of themselves' are endowed with, they are afraid of the world; on the contrary, they seek mental freedom by overcoming obstacles in the psychological realm. Nietzsche says as well that the strong were perfectly described as a caste of warriors, blond beasts, and in this sense, their loyalty to their duties and their self-control were trained through deep discipline (such as was the case in Ancient Greece or Germania), and not by denying all of their pleasures or needs, specially those which would require them to fulfil their ambitions as men amongst their ranks.

For the reason of not being able to overcome obstacles and to cower from the determinations of the World, the weak feel 'guilt'; self-projected hatred or 'bad conscience' is the way to deal with guilt. The weak fail to become independent in the World because they lack independence and the strength to overcome obstacles and

reach their desired goals, and finally, they resent the World and the strong; they try to gain independence in the psychological realm.

In order for them to achieve this independence, they constantly withdraw from all worldly pleasures or anything that blurs their isolation. The pleasure of renouncing the World and becoming independent of it is enormous, such that the resentful person develops a system of denial of the World in an extensive way. In order to gain more and more independence and internal power and to stimulate their 'bad consciences', the weak create and transform guilt into a moral concept by considering their failures as irremediable before "God". They resent themselves for wanting to do what they don't have the strength to achieve, control and overcome obstacles in the way of themselves; they say, then, that they are in aeternal original sin in the eyes of this "God". 'Guilt' before "God" becomes the instrument of torture for themselves; therefore, the weak enter an endless process of self-punishment and search for internal independence.

An important development is born in Western civilization with the weak: The separation between 'Physical World' and 'Mental World' (even in Platonic works this is actually denied from *Plátôn* as far as *Próklos* [of course there is a clear distinction between matter and mind, physical and immaterial things, such as the ideas, but everything is interconnected], and Nietzsche has in mind here christianity), and, consequently, between 'body' and 'mind'. The World for the strong is an extension of themselves, they see the World as completely compatible with themselves; they see no reason to perceive it as beyond them or as standing on top of anything. The weak see the World as unfathomable, as something that cannot be determined, and therefore deny it. We Westerners, according to "Nietzsche", have become adept at repressing and denying our desires and emotions rather than asserting ourselves as we came to be. Natural inclinations, therefore, are victimized and demonized so that the weak unite

totally with their bad conscience and becomes inseparable from it. Reversing the slave morality scenario, however, is seen by “Nietzsche” as possible.

III

“Nietzsche” here analyses the ascetic ideal, and we find four new groups: the ‘sick’, the ‘healthy’, the ‘ascetic priests’ and the ‘free spirits’. The ‘ascetic ideal’ is the practice of one who denies certain pleasures, or the release of emotions, and ascetic practice is idolized and deified as an ideal. This ideal presents itself as the negation of all the wealth that is given in life; in fact, this ideal presents itself as the very negation of life: for someone to deny the pleasures and emotions that are continually stimulated throughout everyday life, he has to withdraw and isolate himself from the flow of present life, in order to materialize a state not yet instantiated; this state in which desires and emotions are not a problem. The ascetic’s ideal is nothing more than a device for trying to preserve a degenerate life; someone who would therefore try to assert their desires and emotions whatever they were, would encounter obstacles and resistance from society, or morality, and ultimately end up frustrated. The frustrated person could, therefore, fall into the desperate belief that his existence would make no sense. However, when faced with the opposition of society, this social and moral resistance against their desires and emotions, this someone could aim to eliminate and deny their own life, that is, deny their desires and emotions in order to guarantee the norms, morals and values. It is mister to say, nonetheless, that the sets of values which Nietzsche says that the ‘healthy’ have are ‘master values’, such as ‘courage’, ‘sagacity’, ‘egoism’, ‘perfectionism’, ‘strength’, ‘manliness or virility’, ‘truthfulness’, ‘loyalty’ &c... Here,

the ascetic's denial of life aims to maintain or preserve stability and values that are values of a slave morality...

Those who idolize the ascetic ideal in order to live are, according to "Nietzsche", the 'sick'. Christian priests, in particular, are considered by him to be the sickest possible. The 'ascetic priests', therefore, are the *preservers* of life, the deniers of it. The healthy are, therefore, those who do not need the ascetic ideal to live (they live in harmony with the World, they do what is needed to be done and go for it); for them, desires and emotions are not problematic, because they do not depend on social and moral norms for their values, for they find and establish their own.

Healthy people can seek and affirm their desires and emotions without opposing them to their values, so they can be happy; whereas the sick find their desires and emotions in conflict with moral and social norms and, therefore, need to repress them and annihilate them into non-existence. Although the sick can overcome this opposition, or conflict, they are never satisfied with their desires and emotions and are therefore unhappy; but this unhappiness is all they know what to do with their lives... Consequently, the sick start to envy the healthy and happy, and for this reason, they start to hate them. The sick, therefore, have what "Nietzsche" calls 'resentment' (*ressentiment*), literally resentment of fortune, satisfaction, and the power of others unlike themselves... The sick then try to poison the healthy so that they will be ashamed of their power, their self-control, their wealth, their beauty, and strength, &c., so that they become aware of the misery that is certainly not theirs, causing them to lower their affirmations of values to the morality of the sick and, finally, come to deny the World... The sick are conditioned, in the first place, to fall into the ilk and trap of the 'ascetic priest' who preaches and advocates the ascetic imperative, because, precisely, they are the ones who require asceticism to live, to merely preserve themselves. The 'ascetic

priest' only draws the sick away from the healthy, causing their process of self-destruction to become such that their resentments are strictly turned to them and they, no longer resent against the healthy themselves.

The healthy become infected with asceticism when it is wedded to the "will for truth". This group of individuals would be those "free spirits" that despite resisting, or denying, the Judeo-Christian morality, *id est*, the morality of the 'ascetic priest', have faith in the search for and only for the truth through science. Science and only science, unlike religion, would be worthy of respect for humanity, an area of non-metaphysical knowledge, to know that it would not presuppose the belief in a World-in-the-beyond - as a repressed desire for reward from the sick -, in a "God", because they found these entities or supposed realities as fictitious before their own reason... For them, life only makes sense in the truth. What, therefore, "Nietzsche" verifies is that the highest metaphysical ascetic degree is found, precisely, in the belief in the search for truth; a metaphysical value, a truth value. They presuppose faith in science and believe in another World beyond life, nature and history. "Nietzsche" will argue, then, that these supposed 'free spirits' are far from free, as they are trapped in the search for the absolute, or the truth; they are attached to this faith as if there were indeed truth - even without having it -, it being supposedly attainable and that they could kneel the World at their feet with their possession. Therefore, Western culture would be infected through philosophy, science, and religion with asceticism...

With the tremendous spread of the disease of asceticism, "Nietzsche" prescribes, great nausea would arise; and if with it were added to the feeling of lamentation, or wailing, in view of the impossibility of its metaphysical project to come to an end, men would reach such an unhealthy point, a view that the ascetic ideal would no longer be used to preserve life, but to finish it. This great disgust and repudiation of a miserable,

meaningless existence would at best lead to total nihilism, even if it were chosen and determined by the will to desire nothing rather than having nothing to desire, not as in an apathetic catalepsy, but annihilation, therefore, would be the worthy, meaningful, and last valuable means to be chosen without free will.

Instead of exhorting the free spirit, one tends to reflect on the following sentence: “As soon as faith in the God of the ascetic ideal is denied, a new problem arises: that of the value of truth.”

- Principle of Non-Maleficence -

After having made this brief very important passage on “The Genealogy of Morals”, it becomes clear to me that moralisms certainly aside and any medical intervention, even if it is just a conversation about the patient’s diet, there already arises sufferings. If we are like a set of elements, composed of essentialities, or even if we are only composed of non-essential elements, which arise, develop and also appear; also with regard to all our aspects, that is, our physiopsychological totalities. We are, therefore, the sum of each of these elements together, like a bundle of flows of immanence; if we are thus given our existing condition, therefore, a minimal alteration that is holistically done to us and, thus, ontologically speaking, I would be another being, or each would be other beings...

So, we would be asked: ‘and what does this have to do with the ethical principle above?’ It is basically the metaphysical dimension of its impossibility, because the condition of a patient, if he consents to the treatment, will certainly never be the same as it was before, nor as he came to the office before, nor when he was in the crib as a baby, nor when he will perish, or what it would be like to strengthen his immune system with a flow of micro-organic material to give him possible defenses against future infections.

Furthermore, there are no guarantees in the medical or veterinary field, or in the raising of animals for slaughter, for example, that the misunderstanding “understood here as physical or psychological damage (or both)” will not be done consciously or involuntarily, even if this is not what was desired by all parties involved. It is enough to see how patients undergoing oncological treatment feel because of cancer, in which traditional techniques are extremely harmful or invasive, with a high chance of death caused by the treatment. Thus, this principle is virtually impossible in traditional allopathic medicine (including veterinary) and virtually most treatments of what academia calls the so-called “scientific medicine” (of which there is plenty of influence of capital or money from pharmaceutical industries who have conflicting profit interest in not actually curing any patients at all).

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